

A First *Introduction* to Open Science

May 2021, TWAS UNESCO webinar

Useful links

Open Access to publications

Directory of Open Access Journals <https://doaj.org> and journals that don't have Article Processing Charges (APCs) <https://bit.ly/2YNWAFn>

Choose the right journal or publisher for your research <https://thinkchecksubmit.org>

Sherpa Romeo online resource that aggregates and analyses publisher open access policies from around the world and provides summaries of publisher copyright and open access archiving policies on a journal-by-journal basis <https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/romeo>

Shareyourpaper.org tool to check publisher's permissions and versions of the article (for non open access articles) and upload articles on Zenodo <https://shareyourpaper.org>

Discovery of open access content

- **Open Access Button** <https://openaccessbutton.org>
- **Unpaywall** <http://unpaywall.org>
- **CORE Discovery** <https://core.ac.uk/services/discovery>
- **OpenAIRE Explore** <https://explore.openaire.eu>
- **BASE Search** <https://www.base-search.net>

Directory of Open Access Books <https://doabooks.org>

Zenodo repository <https://zenodo.org>

Preprints resources <https://asapbio.org/preprint-info>,
<https://asapbio.org/preprints-and-covid-19>, <https://asapbio.org/public>

Pascal Braak, Hans de Jonge, Giulia Trentacosti, Irene Verhagen, & Saskia Woutersen-Windhauer. (2020, October 28). Guide to Creative Commons for Scholarly Publications and Educational Resources (Version final). Zenodo.
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4090923>

Research Data Management

How to make your data FAIR: <https://www.openaire.eu/how-to-make-your-data-fair>

How to find a trustworthy repository for your data:
<https://www.openaire.eu/find-trustworthy-data-repository>

How do I license my research data:
<https://www.openaire.eu/how-do-i-license-my-research-data>

Can I reuse someone else's research data?
<https://www.openaire.eu/can-i-reuse-someone-else-research-data>

Data Management Expert Guide:
<https://www.cessda.eu/Training/Training-Resources/Library/Data-Management-Expert-Guide>

Open Science

UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science:
<https://en.unesco.org/science-sustainable-future/open-science/recommendation>

Erin C McKiernan et al. 2016, How open science helps researchers succeed
<https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.16800.001>

Open Science MOOC: <https://opensciencemooc.eu>

Open Science Framework - a free, open platform to support your research and enable collaboration <https://osf.io>

FOSTER Open Science Training Toolkit: <https://www.fosteropenscience.eu/toolkit>

A collection of use cases from The Netherlands

[A Collection of Open Science Use Cases](#)

Profiles in Open and a list of Scholarly research on the benefits of Open

<https://www.orfg.org/reading-list>

An Introduction to Open Science

<https://zenodo.org/record/4883033>

Presentation from this webinar

Open Science Myths and Misconceptions

<https://zenodo.org/record/4883635>

Presentation from this webinar